

Benzophenone and methyl orange sensitized photooxidation of flavone and 4'-methoxy flavone : A comparative study

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Abstract : Benzophenone and methyl orange sensitized photooxidation of flavone and 4-methoxy flavone (1a and b) by UV light in presence of air gave different products. With benzophenone where substrate is in the excited state, it gave 2a and b and with methyl orange and where oxygen is in the excited state, it gave 3a and b. The structures of the products have been confirmed by spectral and elemental analyses.

Keywords : UV, photooxidation, flavone, 4-methoxy flavone.

Introduction

Photochemistry of organic compounds has been a vast field of research since a long time. Singlet oxygen plays an important role in animal metabolism. It has been found to have damaging effects in human beings. The role of singlet oxygen in a photochemical reaction has been studied widely¹⁻⁶. Photooxygenation of flavones has also been studied by Matsuura and Waiss⁷⁻¹². But very little work has been done on comparative study with benzophenone and a dye sensitized photooxidations¹³⁻¹⁸.

The photooxidations can be carried out with singlet molecular oxygen or with ground state molecular oxygen. The singlet oxygen i.e. the excited state of oxygen is generated photochemically using a suitable sensitizer, e.g. dye. The singlet oxygen then reacts with the substrate molecule to give the product, which are generally endoperoxides. The reaction is known as Type-II Backstrom mechanism. If some other sensitizer e.g. benzophenone is used then the substrate molecule gets excited and the oxygen reacts in the ground state (Type-I Backstrom mechanism) and the products are generally hydroperoxides. In general a photooxidation reaction can be depicted as follows :

Results and discussion

Flavone and 4-methoxy flavone (1a and b) when irradiated by UV light in presence of benzophenone gave the products 2a and b (Scheme 1). However, when flavone and 4'-methoxy flavone are irradiated in presence of methyl orange gave products 3a and b (Scheme 2).

With benzophenone as a sensitizer, the flavone molecule is excited, because the triplet state of flavone (259 kJ/mol) is of lower energy than that of the benzophenone (289 kJ/mol), whereas triplet energy of methyl orange is lower than that of flavone, hence methyl orange can not sensitize flavone, and the reaction proceed through the sensitization of ground state oxygen to singlet excited oxygen followed by its reaction with substrate^{19,20}. It had been suggested previously by Schenck *et al*²¹ that such reaction involved the formation of an intermediate ³Σ oxygen substrate complex. Hence it could be possible that the reaction involves methyl orange sensitization of oxygen followed by its reaction with substrate molecule to form endoperoxide, which further reduced to the product.

The structures of products have been confirmed by spectral and elemental analyses. The formation of the product 2a has been confirmed by the appearance of phe-

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

nolic OH str. at 3150 cm^{-1} and aliphatic CH str. at 2924 cm^{-1} in IR spectrum and a set of triplet and quartet peak at δ 1.3 and 3.0 due to C_2H_5 group and a singlet at δ 10.5 due to phenolic OH in ^1H NMR spectrum which are not present in IR, ^1H NMR spectra of the reactant (1a).

The formation of product 2b has been confirmed by the appearance of phenolic OH str. at 3148 cm^{-1} in IR spectrum and a set of triplet and quartet peak at δ 1.3 and 3.1–3.8 confirming the presence of ethyl group in the product.

Similarly in the IR spectrum of the product 3a two new bands were observed at 3428 cm^{-1} due to phenolic

OH str. and $2924, 2852\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the aliphatic region due to ethyl group of the product which were absent in the reactant spectrum. The ^1H NMR spectrum of the product shows phenolic and alcoholic OH group absorptions at δ 12.5 and 5.0 respectively. The set of triplet and quartet at δ 1.1 and 3.2 due to ethyl group and a singlet at δ 4.1 due to CHOH protons further support the product formation.

The formation of product 3b was confirmed by the appearance of phenolic OH str. at 3143 cm^{-1} in IR spectrum of the product, which was not present in the reactant spectrum. The ^1H NMR spectrum of the product

Note

shows phenolic and alcoholic OH protons at δ 12.5 and 5.0 respectively and a set of triplet quartet peak at δ 1.0 and 3.2 due to ethyl group of the product. The spectral data and physical properties of products **2a**, **2b**, **3a** and **3b** have been given in Tables 1 and 2. The fragmentation patterns of these products have been given in Figs. 1 and 2.

Table 1. Physical data of products **2a**, **2b**, **3a** and **3b**

Sl. no.	Compds. (Empirical formula), Colour	M.p. (°C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)		Yield (%)
			C	H	
1.	(2a) C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₃ Light yellow	129	77.47 (77.27)	6.28 (6.28)	75
2.	(2b) C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₄ Yellow	132	72.90 (72.48)	6.44 (6.04)	65
3.	(3a) C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₅ Dark yellow	121	68.82 (67.54)	6.10 (5.96)	85
4.	(3b) C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₆ Yellow	157	65.37 (65.06)	6.41 (6.02)	80

Table 2. IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and Mass spectral data of products **2a**, **2b**, **3a** and **3b**

Compds.	IR (cm ⁻¹)	¹ H NMR (δ , ppm)	¹³ C NMR (δ , ppm)	FAB Mass (<i>m/z</i>)
2a 	3150 (phenolic -OH str.), 3020 (arom. C-H str.), 2924 (aliph. C-H str.), 1650 (C=O str.), 1600 (C=C str.), 1400 (C-O str., phenolic), 1120 (O-C ₂ H ₅ str.), 700-750 (arom. C-H bend)	1.3 (3H, t, CH ₃), 3.0 (2H, q, OCH ₂), 5.5 (1H, s, olefinic-H), 7.0-7.5 (5H, m, aromatic-H), 10.5 (1H, s, OH), 6.5-7.9 (4H, m, C ₆ H ₄ -OH)	20.1 (CH ₃), 45.1 (OCH ₂), 118-120 (olefinic carbons), 126-138 (aromatic ring carbons), 192 (CO carbon)	268 [M ⁺], 77 (base peak), 251, 223, 207, 178, 121, 88, 77 (other fragment peaks)
2b 	3148 (phenolic -OH str.), 3062.1 (arom. CH str.), 2983.1 (aliph. C-H str.), 1645.3 (C=O str.)	1.3 (3H, t, CH ₃), 3.1-3.8 (2H, q, O-CH ₂), 3H, s, OCH ₃ , 5.5 (1H, s, olefinic-H), 7.1-7.6 (4H, m, C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃), 10.7 (1H, s, OH), 6.5-7.9 (4H, m, C ₆ H ₄ -OH)	20 (CH ₃), 45.3 (OCH ₂), 35 (OCH ₃), 118-120 (olefinic carbons), 126-138 (aromatic ring carbons), 192 (CO carbon)	298 [M ⁺], 134 (base peak), 254, 237, 209, 189, 165, 149, 121, 91 (other fragment peaks)
3a 	3428 (OH str.), 1645 (C=O str.), 1604 (C=C str.), 1442 (C-O str.)	4.1 (1H, s, CH-CO), 5.0 (2H, s, OH), 7.0-7.8 (5H, m, C ₆ H ₅), 11.8 (1H, s, aromatic OH), 6.3-7.1 (4H, m, C ₆ H ₄ -OH)	19.0 (CH ₃), 42 (OCH ₂), 97.2 (CHOH), 118.3 (COH), 128-136 (aromatic ring carbons), 193 (CO carbon)	302 [M ⁺], 149 (base peak), 285, 227, 223, 198, 151, 119, 103, 93, 77 (other fragment peaks)

Table-2 (contd.)

3b 	3143 (OH str.),	1.0 (3H, t, CH ₃),	19.0 (CH ₃),	332 [M ⁺],
	3026 (arom. CH str.),	3.2 (2H, q, OCH ₂),	42 (OCH ₂ , OCH ₃),	88 (base peak),
	2922.1 (allph. C-H str.),	3.8 (3H, s, OCH ₃),	97.2 (CHOH),	332, 274, 240, 210,
	1456 (C-O str.),	4.1 (1H, s, CH-CO),	118.3 (COH),	162, 230, 107, 105,
		5.0 (2H, s, OH),	125-139 (aromatic ring carbons),	88 (other fragment peaks)
		7.2 (4H, m, C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃),	192 (CO carbon)	
	12.5 (1H, s, aromatic OH),			
	6.3-7.1 (4H, m, C ₆ H ₄ -OH)			

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Experimental

Synthesis : The flavones were synthesized by bromination of 2'-hydroxy chalcones in alcohol followed by dehydrobromination of 2'-hydroxy chalcones dibromide^{22,23}.

Benzophenone sensitized photooxidation of flavone and 4-methoxy flavone : The substrate (2 g) was dissolved in dry and distilled ethanol (200 ml). Benzophenone was added as a sensitizer and solution was irradiated by medium pressure mercury vapour lamp (250 W) in an immersion well photoreactor. The temperature of reaction mixture was kept constant by continuous water circulation and air was continuously bubbled through the solution with the help of an aerator. The progress of the

reaction was monitored by TLC. The reaction completed in 49 and 45 h respectively and the irradiation was stopped, the solution was concentrated on a water bath under reduced pressure and was left over night where upon yellow solid separated out, which was filtered, washed, dried and recrystallized from ethanol.

Methyl orange sensitized photooxidation of flavone and 4'-methoxy flavone : The reaction was carried out in the same manner as above, instead of benzophenone, methyl orange was used as a sensitizer. The reaction completed in 47 and 40 h respectively. The reaction mixture was concentrated by distillation under reduced pressure after removing the dye by animal charcoal treatment and was left over night, a solid separated out which was filtered, washed, dried and recrystallized.

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